

Basal Cell Carcinoma During Pregnancy: Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Introduction. Basal cell carcinoma during pregnancy is an entity with an incidence of one case per one thousand pregnant women. It requires timely management, as it may present aggressive behavior and has both psychological and clinical implications for the treatment of the mother and the fetus.

Case Report. A 31-year-old woman at 37 weeks of gestation presented for prenatal care, with a history of gravida 3, para 1, abortion 1, and no family history of cancer. During her initial evaluation, an abdominal dermatologic lesion was noted. At 40 weeks of gestation, she was admitted for labor induction due to gestational age and an amniotic fluid index of 6 cm, which was within normal limits but near the lower threshold. A single live female newborn was delivered with APGAR scores of 8/9. The patient was discharged 24 hours later and referred to dermatology where a biopsy was performed due to suspicion of basal cell carcinoma. Surgical excision with wide margins was subsequently carried out without complications, and the final histopathological report confirmed pigmented nodular basal cell carcinoma with negative margins. The patient experienced a favorable postoperative course.

Conclusion. We present the clinical case of a pregnant patient with an abdominal dermatologic lesion who underwent surgical excision with good clinical progress; the lesion was reported as pigmented nodular basal cell carcinoma.

KEYWORDS: Basal cell carcinoma. Pregnancy with basal cell carcinoma.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Basal cell carcinoma (BCC) is a slow-growing tumor that originates from the non-keratinized cells of the basal layer of the epidermis and develops in sun-exposed areas between the third and sixth decades of life.¹

Breast cancer, cervical cancer, malignant melanoma, and lymphomas are the most common cancers that occur during pregnancy.²

The incidence of this type of cancer in pregnant women is relatively low, at approximately one case per thousand pregnancies.³

Basal cell carcinoma has increased in recent years worldwide, with a more pronounced rise in tropical countries due to inappropriate behaviors such as sun exposure from childhood, the use of tanning beds, and applying sunscreen only once a day.⁴

An increase in cancer rates during pregnancy can be anticipated based on the rising incidence of BCC in young women, combined with the postponement of motherhood until the third and fourth decades of life.⁵

Clinically, superficial basal cell carcinoma may resemble inflammatory dermatoses such as eczema or psoriasis; therefore, the diagnosis of superficial basal cell carcinoma

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should be considered in the presence of a persistent erythematous, scaly plaque.⁶

It often appears as a shiny pimple or a pearly bump on the surface of the skin. Small blood vessels may be visible on or around this bump, and it may bleed easily when traumatized or irritated. Frequently, these lesions do not heal spontaneously.⁸

Nodular basal cell carcinoma is the most common variant. It is characterized by arborizing (branching) vessels and the presence of a single ulceration and is more common in individuals with darker skin. On dermoscopy, pigmented nodular basal cell carcinoma shows large blue oval nests (blue clods), blue dots and globules, and branching (arborizing) vessels.⁷

It usually presents as a shiny, pink or skin-colored papule or nodule with superficial telangiectasias, appearing on the shoulders, face—especially the nose, forehead, cheeks, nasolabial folds, and eyelids—as well as on the chest or back, and multiple lesions may be present.⁷

Therefore, treatment is based on the characteristics of the tumor, the trimester of pregnancy, and the potential consequences for gestation, with surgical excision with margins being the standard treatment. Mohs surgery may be considered in specific cases, especially in facial areas or in tumors at risk of recurrence.⁹

Likewise, patients treated with 200 mg of sonidegib in a study by Sanmartín O. et al. showed an objective response to treatment, with a mean time to response of four months.¹⁰

However, due to the risk of congenital defects, pregnant women or women who may become pregnant should not use any of these medications

Figure 1: Initial dermatological lesion identified by dermoscopy.

Figure 2: Lesion on the abdomen, not enlarged.

II. CASE REPORT

A 31-year-old patient with a history of menarche at age 13, gravida 3, para 1, abortion 1, denied a family history of cancer or frequent and prolonged sun exposure. At 37 weeks of gestation, ultrasound screening showed a single live fetus in longitudinal cephalic presentation, with an anterior corporal placenta.

At her first prenatal visit to our hospital, a dermatology consultation was requested due to a dermatologic lesion on the abdomen, in the left hypochondrial region. The lesion appeared as a plaque-like neoplasm measuring approximately 1 cm × 9 mm, irregular in shape, brown–black in color with well-defined borders. Dermoscopic examination revealed shiny white structures on its surface, as well as a blue veil and pseudopods at the periphery of the lesion; therefore, a biopsy was scheduled (Figures 1 and 2).

The patient returned for her second visit one week later and was prescribed nystatin due to infectious vaginitis. However, 72 hours later, hospital admission was decided due to a term pregnancy and an amniotic fluid index of 6 cm, within normal range but close to the lower limit, and labor induction was initiated.

With good in-hospital evolution, a female newborn was delivered vaginally later that day, with an Apgar score of 8/9, at 40 weeks of gestation, weighing 3,125 g, and with an estimated uterine blood loss of 250 mL.

Given the favorable evolution of both mother and newborn, discharge was decided the following day.

During hospitalization, the patient was evaluated by the dermatology service, which scheduled an incisional biopsy of the dermatologic lesion. The biopsy was performed 48 hours postpartum without complications, and sutures were removed 12 days later.

Biopsy results were delivered three weeks after suture removal, showing findings compatible with nodular basal cell carcinoma with positive peripheral margins; therefore, surgical excision of the lesion with margin enlargement was scheduled.

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The dermatologic lesion was excised with widened margins three months later, without complications, with good clinical evolution and proper wound healing, after which sutures were removed.

The final histopathology report of the excision specimen showed negative margins for neoplastic cells. Consequently, follow-up was scheduled every 3 to 6 months, along with photoprotection measures every 4 hours on sun-exposed areas.

DISCUSSION

Cases of melanoma during pregnancy are known to be associated with poor prognosis; however, basal cell carcinoma (BCC) during pregnancy is rare. We present a case in which the dermatologic lesion, due to its appearance, mimicked melanoma but was ultimately ruled out. Consequently, there is limited knowledge regarding BCC in pregnant women.

In this case, no risk factors such as sun exposure or severe sunburns were identified. As noted by Cahoon EK et al., other risk factors include scars, immunosuppression, and, in women, exposure to exogenous hormones such as oral contraceptives and hormone replacement therapy, estrogenic medications that increase the risk of phototoxicity and photocarcinogenesis, none of which were reported by the patient.¹²

Management was appropriate, avoiding pharmacological therapy due to potential fetal harm. Surgical excision was therefore performed postpartum, unlike the case reported by Galen H. Fisher et al., in which a 42-year-old patient with a rapidly growing BCC on the face underwent excision at 36 weeks of gestation under local anesthesia.¹³

III. CONCLUSIONS

The presentation of basal cell carcinoma during pregnancy is extremely rare. However, when it occurs, a surgical approach is necessary, which may vary depending on the growth of the dermatologic lesion. In the present case, surgical excision was successfully performed postpartum.

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